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Abstract: In the article, the author thinks about increasing labor efficiency and labor productivity. According to him, the concept of practical labor efficiency allows to express the productivity of labor in an enterprise or industry. In a society where the labor process is organized taking these factors into account, labor efficiency in enterprises and organizations increases gradually. Also, the article emphasizes that labor productivity occurs in economic, political and spiritual forms. If the employees' work in the workplace meets the criteria, it is considered productive and effective, while the scale of their problems indicates that it is being carried out ineffectively. At the same time, by studying these criteria of labor efficiency, it is possible to identify the processes that hinder its improvement. The chapter reveals that the need to develop the material and technical base of these problems remains today, new situations arise as a result of diversification of production, and the slow implementation of innovative technologies in production in places.

Keywords: labor productivity, actual labor productivity, available labor productivity, potential labor productivity, the impact of reforms on labor productivity, factors that reduce labor productivity, opportunities to increase labor productivity.

Today, the main goal of any state is to increase the material well-being and cultural level of the population. The "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy also pays special attention to the issues of increasing the well-being of the population through sustainable economic growth in the republic over the next seven years. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to take a place among the countries with above-average incomes through sustainable economic growth, further improve the pace of development of the country's economy, and especially to continuously increase its efficiency. Because economic efficiency is directly related, first of all, to the rapid growth of social labor productivity. Social labor productivity is of decisive importance in the socio-economic development of the country. Labor productivity is one of the main determinants of production efficiency, in which one can see the further increase in the activity of people in production. Productivity is the level of achieving maximum results using the total available resources (cash and financial assets).

Currently, increasing labor productivity creates the basis for increasing wages and other material incomes of workers in production and, thereby, increasing the well-being of the population. After all, the higher the labor productivity, the higher the wages, which further increases the material well-being of citizens.

From the experience of developed countries, it can be seen that in the process of building a new society, a number of issues arise that require comprehensive and in-depth study and analysis. Positive solutions to these issues will lead to successful activities in a market economy. Of course, one of such problems is the problems in the labor sphere, which relate to the social and economic spheres of society. The labor productivity indicator, in addition to showing the level of effective use of labor resources, reflects the development of the country's economy. Therefore, the issues of increasing labor efficiency are among the most

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urgent issues today. Our country's economy is developing rapidly, and the share of industry in its structure is increasing.. This growth rate was discussed at a videoconference meeting chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 26, 2022 to discuss the development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 and its implementation this year. It was noted that a number of measures were identified for the comprehensive and accelerated development of economic sectors, the creation of modern jobs and poverty reduction, in particular, the goal is to increase the volume of gross domestic product by \$ 100 billion in the next five years. It was especially noted that it is planned to increase the production of industrial products by 1.4 times and reduce the poverty level by at least 2 times. Of course, structural changes in the republic to produce competitive finished products and establish a modern service system will be carried out by increasing labor productivity. There are ways to increase productivity, and they are:

Using modern technologies. The more modern technologies are used in business entities, the higher the level of labor productivity in enterprises. Training and improving the skills of employees. Studies show that the creation of free advanced training courses for employees allows you to increase labor productivity in the enterprise. Improving working conditions. Creating good conditions for employees is the most effective way to increase labor productivity. Improving organizational management. Proper distribution of working time.

First, if we explain the dictionary meaning of the concept of efficiency, in a number of scientific literature (efficiency - English) (efficientia - Latin) it has several translation interpretations. The rather widespread expression "efficiency" can be explained with concepts such as "effectiveness, productivity, mobility and operability". The concept of efficiency has been the subject of various scientific studies by many researchers, who have expressed their views. For example, prominent scientists of the republic have also expressed their views on the concept of efficiency. In particular, academician Q.Kh. Abdurakhmonov defines it as follows: "The concept of efficiency is an extremely broad concept, it reflects the ratio of the result obtained to the costs."

Labor productivity in industrial enterprises is an important indicator of labor efficiency, the result of which is expressed in the form of labor output (in units of time or value). Labor efficiency labor productivity. Productivity is defined as a concept that expresses the level of labor effectiveness. In some cases, this refers to the activities of a specific employee at a specific workplace, and in other cases, to the social production process at the societal level. There are specific methods for measuring labor productivity in these entities. It is noteworthy that these methods are constantly being improved. In particular, until recently, productivity was determined based on the amount of products produced in a certain period - number, volume, etc. Today, it is determined not only by the amount of products produced over a certain period of time, but also by the labor costs incurred in producing the product, the amount of income from product sales, and a number of other similar indicators and parameters.

Experts have developed and recommended a whole system of concepts used to determine productivity, as well as formulas used in this. The diversity of concepts is not accidental. Because, for example, the concept of "actual productivity" allows us to express the real output of labor in an enterprise or industry (also on a community scale). In sources devoted to the topic, it is proposed to determine actual productivity based on the following formula:

$$\text{Mu} = \text{Mh} / \text{Mx},$$

where: Mu – productivity; Mh – product volume; Mx – labor costs.

In this case, it is necessary to pay attention to the essence of the issue. Productivity does not mean simply measuring the products created and services provided at a certain time. Its fundamental goals are related to other needs. Any production activity must be improved, otherwise at some point it will no longer be able to satisfy existing needs. In order to improve it, it is necessary to identify not only the results of the current activity, but also the possibilities for increasing its output. To do this, while measuring the productivity of people's activities at work, it is necessary to calculate in advance how much product can be produced under existing conditions. This measurement allows you to improve the labor process and find unrealized opportunities. Its final result is expressed using the concept of "net productivity". In other words, net productivity is a unit that indicates the volume of product that can be produced under existing conditions when all opportunities are used.

Reducing the gap between actual and actual productivity is not easy. To do this, it is necessary to focus on a number of factors. For example, this gap cannot be eliminated without achieving the most efficient use of the material and technical base at the disposal of an institution or firm. It is necessary to use the existing opportunities more rationally to increase the volume and variety of products and services. Diversification of production can also be effective. The adoption of developments developed and recommended in scientific institutions plays a special role in reducing this gap. There is no need to justify this: developments give greater productivity and efficiency to the production process, radically improve the activities of the enterprise.

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